

A Revenue Forecast Comparison for the Automobile Industry Using Neural and Linear Regression

Uma Comparação de Previsão de Receita para a Indústria Automobilística Usando Neurais e Regressão Linear
Una comparación de pronósticos de ingresos para la industria automotriz mediante regresión neuronal y linea

Recebido
Received
Recibido

Fevereiro, 2025
February, 2025
Febrero, 2025

Aceito
Accepted
Aceptado

Março, 2025
March, 2025
Marzo, 2025

Publicado
Published
Publicado

Abril, 2024
April, 2024
Abril, 2024

<https://git.fateczl.edu.br>

e_ISSN
2965-3339

DOI
10.29327/2384439.3.3-4

São Paulo
v. 3 | n. 3
v. 3 | i. 3

e33308

Abril-Junho
April-June
Abril-Junio
2025

Roberto Giro Moori¹

roberto.g.moori@gmail.com

Andre Ng¹

a_ng@bol.com.br

Roberto Ramos de Morais¹

1125656@mackenzie.br

Plácido de Jesus da Silva Leitão Junior¹

placido.leitao@mackenzie.br

1 – Mackenzie Presbyterian University

Abstract: Artificial neural networks (ANNs) are tools used in the construction of complex system models. Their primary characteristics include learning and reducing the volume of data for modeling purposes. This exploratory study compared the performance of models based on multiple linear regression and neural networks in forecasting the revenues of the automotive industry. We used secondary data collected from the National Association of Automotive Vehicle Manufacturers - ANFAVEA (2002) for the period from 1980 to 2001. The results showed that the average error of the forecast model based on neural networks was smaller than the model based on multiple linear regression.

Keywords: *Automobile industry; revenue; neural networks; linear regression.*

Resumo: Redes neurais artificiais (RNAs) são ferramentas utilizadas na construção de modelos de sistemas complexos. Suas principais características incluem: aprendizado e redução do volume de dados para a modelagem. Este estudo exploratório comparou o desempenho dos modelos baseados em regressão linear múltipla e das redes neurais para prever as receitas da indústria automobilística. Foram utilizados dados secundários, referentes ao período de 1980 a 2001, coletados da ANFAVEA (2002). Os resultados mostraram que o erro médio do modelo de previsão baseado em redes neurais foi menor do que o modelo baseado em regressão linear múltipla.

Palavras-chave: Indústria automobilística; receita; redes neurais; regressão linear.

Resumen: Las redes neuronales artificiales (RNA) son herramientas que se utilizan para construir modelos de sistemas complejos. Sus principales características incluyen: aprender y reducir el volumen de datos para modelar. Este estudio exploratorio comparó el rendimiento de modelos basados en regresión lineal múltiple y redes neuronales para predecir los ingresos en la industria del automóvil. Se utilizaron datos secundarios, referidos al período de 1980 a 2001, recogidos de ANFAVEA (2002). Los resultados mostraron que el error promedio del modelo de predicción

basado en redes neuronales fue menor que el del modelo basado en regresión lineal múltiple.

Palabras clave: *Industria automotriz; ganancia; redes neuronales; regresión lineal.*

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, Brazil has been highlighted as one of the emerging economies with the capacity to generate new perspectives for the socioeconomic development of Latin America. According to projections, R\$95 billion will be invested in the country's already established automobile industry by 2030 (Moliterno, 2024). With increased competitiveness, automobile manufacturers are adopting increasingly modern and lean production techniques. Many of the production processes adopted in Brazil will be exported to other factories worldwide (Silva, 2000, p. B7). Naturally, it is important to consider competitiveness in the strategies adopted by the industry. However, Ohmae (1998, p. 68) argues that when adopting a strategy, it should not be prioritized. Before that, full attention is given to the needs and added value of the products delivered to customers, as well as organizing the business system that plans, manufactures, and sells them. Business planning is an everyday activity for any type of company, regardless of its size or industry. It is imperative that companies have practical approaches to forecasting and that it be an integral part of business planning. Planning is continually underway in all areas, whether formally or informally. Every day, managers determine the course of action they will take in the future without knowing what the future holds. Countless decisions make up planning itself or are derived from it. They order inventory without knowing what sales will be, purchase new equipment despite uncertainty about product demand, and make investments without knowing what the profits will be. Managers are always trying to make more accurate estimates of what will happen in the future, given the uncertainty. Making accurate estimates is the primary purpose of forecasting, which serves as the input for business strategies such as planning new facilities, production planning, workforce scheduling, and other related activities.

In this context of competitiveness and the need to add value to products purchased by customers, this study aimed to compare the performance of a revenue forecasting model based on a neural network and a forecasting model based on multiple linear regression. The analysis of revenue forecasts for the national automobile industry considered domestic sales, vehicle exports and investments made between 1980 and 2001.

By comparing the performance of forecasting models based on neural networks and multiple linear regression to deal with inaccurate knowledge, imprecise information or randomness of variables involved in the revenue of the automobile industry, we are contributing to the development of alternatives in sales forecast formulations and, consequently, in production sequencing, workforce sizing, purchasing and other supply chain management activities. Finally, when results appear that are firmly based on objective and well-founded concepts so that the conditions of applicability, advantages and limitations of the new techniques become clear, this technique will certainly come to be accepted by the community and be incorporated into the body of knowledge at the service of science and technology, generating new businesses, new companies and, consequently, new jobs, which is the ultimate purpose of this research.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 MULTIPLE LINEAR REGRESSION

Multiple linear regression is a powerful and flexible method for analyzing the association between a dependent variable and one or more independent variables. It can be used to (a) determine whether the independent variables explain significant variation in the dependent variable, i.e., whether a relationship exists; (b) determine how much of the variation in the dependent variable can be explained by the independent variables, i.e., the strength of the relationship; (c) determine the structure or form of the relationship, the mathematical equation that relates the independent and dependent variables; (d) predict the values of the dependent variable; and (e) control for other independent variables when evaluating the contributions of a specific variable or set of variables. The general form of the multiple regression model is $Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \dots + \beta_k X_k + e$, which is estimated by the following equation: $\hat{Y} = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + b_3 X_3 + \dots + b_k X_k$.

The coefficient “a” represents the intercept, and the “b’s” are the partial regression coefficients. The least squares criterion estimates the parameters in such a way as to minimize the total squared error (SQ_{res}). This process also maximizes the correlation between the effective values and Y, as well as the predictive values \hat{Y} .

The statistics associated with multiple regression are as follows:

- **Adjusted R²:** R² or the coefficient of multiple determination, is adjusted for the number of independent variables and sample size to account for diminishing returns. After the first few variables, additional independent variables make only a minor contribution to the overall model.
- **Coefficient of multiple determination:** The strength of association in multiple regression is measured by the square of the multiple correlation coefficient, R², which is also known as the coefficient of multiple determination.
- **F-test:** The F-test is used to test the null hypothesis that the coefficient of determination in the population, R^2_{pop} , is zero. This is equivalent to testing the null hypothesis $H_0: \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 \dots = \beta_k = 0$. The test statistic is F-distributed with k and (n – k – 1) degrees of freedom.
- **Partial F-Test:** One can test the significance of a partial regression coefficient, β_i of X_i , using an incremental F statistic. The incremental F statistic is based on the increase in the explained sum of squares resulting from adding the independent variable X_i to the regression equation after all other independent variables have been included.
- **t- Test:** Tests whether the relationship between the dependent and independent variables is significant, i.e., indirectly tests the population correlation coefficient. This test is equivalent to the partial F-test.

- **Partial regression coefficient:** The partial regression coefficient, b_1 , denotes the change in the predictive value \hat{Y} per unit change in X_1 when the other independent variables, X_2 through X_k , are held constant. It can also be interpreted as the bivariate regression coefficient, "b", for the regression of Y on the residuals of X_1 , when the effects of X_2 through X_k have been removed from X_1 .

One of the problems that occur when using multiple linear regression in the time series is:

- a) Multicollinearity. In this case, it is necessary to determine whether the chosen variables are not exactly linear functions of each other. This can produce a high R^2 and lead to erroneous conclusions about the model;
- b) Heteroscedasticity. The construction of the predictive model assumes that the variance of the data and the erratic term "e" remains constant over time (homoscedasticity). Today, with the development of robust statistical analysis techniques, it is known that this assumption is easily violated and;
- c) series size. A very long series can cause some of the variables to lose their intrinsic information. Short series may be biased. A widely used method to validate multiple linear regression is the Durbin-Watson "d" test (GUJARATI, 2000, p. 422).

Although independent variables can explain the variation in the dependent variable, this does not necessarily imply causality. The use of terms such as dependent or criterion variable, independent variable, predictor, or predictor in regression analysis derives from the mathematical relationship between the variables. These terms do not imply that the criterion variable is dependent on the independent variables in a causal sense. The objective of regression analysis is the nature and degree of association between variables; it does not imply or assume any causality. The basic premise of multiple regression is that the model includes all important and relevant variables. If an important variable is omitted, the model's predictive ability is reduced. Furthermore, if the omitted variable is correlated with an included variable, the estimated coefficient of the latter will reflect the combined effect of both variables. Other limitations considered for the application of multiple regression are:

- a. The model is based on collected data that represents certain environmental conditions. If these conditions change, the model will no longer reflect the current situation and may lead to erroneous judgments;
- b. the model's predictive ability, reflected by R^2 , may become significantly reduced if the prediction is based on values of the independent variables that are extreme compared to the values of these same variables used to estimate the model parameters and;
- c. The model is surrounded by the methodology associated with data collection, including sample size and measurements employed.

2.2 NEURAL NETWORKS

Neural networks are computer systems implemented in hardware or software that mimic the abilities of the biological nervous system by using many simple, interconnected artificial neurons (Loesch & Sari, 1996). Artificial neurons are simple emulations of biological neurons, which receive information from sensors or other artificial neurons. Neural networks function through their artificial neurons, which process their data using logical parallelism (for all neurons in the same layer) combined with serial operations (when information from one layer is transferred to neurons in another layer). Three main characteristics describe a neural network and that contribute to its functional ability: structure, dynamics and learning of the neural system.

Structure: A computational information processing unit or neuron is fundamental to the operation of a neural network. Haykin (2001, 36) identifies three basic elements in a neural model (Figure 1):

- a) A set of synapses or connecting links, each characterized by its weight or strength. A signal x_j at the input of synapse j connected to neuron k is multiplied by the synaptic weight w_{kj} , where k refers to the neuron in question and j refers to the input terminal of the synapse to which the weight refers;
- b) an adder to add the input signals, weighted by the respective neuron synapses and;
- c) An activation function to constrain the amplitude of a neuron's output. The activation function is also referred to as a constraint function since it constrains (limits) the allowable range of amplitude of the output signal to a finite value.

Figure 1: Model of an artificial neuron

Source: the authors.

Haykin 's (2001) neural model also includes an externally applied bias. The bias has the effect of increasing or decreasing the net input to the activation function, depending on whether it is positive or negative, respectively.

An activation function defines the output of computational processing units. The main types of activation functions are linear, sigmoid, hyperbolic tangent, and radial basis.

The structure of neurons is closely linked to the learning algorithm used to train the network. Haykin (2001) identifies three fundamentally different classes of network architecture:

- a) Single-layer feedforward networks. Neurons organized in layers, in the simplest form of a layered network, have an input layer of source nodes that projects onto an output layer of neurons (computational nodes);
- b) Multilayer feedforward networks. The second class of feedforward neural networks is distinguished by the presence of one or more hidden layers, whose computational nodes are correspondingly referred to as hidden neurons or hidden units. Figure 2 represents a fully connected, multilayer neural network. The function of the hidden neurons is to intervene between the outer layer and the network's output, thereby facilitating the process. By adding one or more hidden layers, the network becomes capable of extracting higher-order statistics. The ability of hidden neurons to extract higher-order statistics is particularly valuable when the size of the input layer is large;
- c) recurrent networks. A recurrent neural network is distinguished from a feedforward neural network by having at least one feedback loop. A recurrent network might consist, for example, of a single layer of neurons, with each neuron feeding its output signal back to the inputs of all the other neurons.

Figure 2: Neural Network Model

Source: the authors.

Dynamics: The processing units operate as follows: each one receives one or more input signals from the units of units connected to it. These signals are multiplied by the weights of their respective connections and added together, producing the so-called activity level. The resulting value will be used as input to the activation function, which will process it and generate the neuron output. This output will then be passed on to the following processing units (CARTACHO et al., 2002).

Learning: Neural networks can learn from examples and make interpolations and extrapolations of what they have learned. A set of well-defined procedures for adapting the parameters of a neural network so that it can learn a given function is called a learning algorithm. There is no single learning algorithm. We have a set of tools represented by several algorithms, each with its advantages and disadvantages (BRAGA et al., 2000). These algorithms differ primarily in how the weights are adjusted. Several methods for training networks have been developed, and they can be grouped into two main paradigms:

- a) Supervised learning. This learning method is the most common in training neural networks, both weighted and unweighted neurons. It is called

supervised learning because the desired input and output for the network are provided by an external supervisor (teacher). The goal is to adjust the network parameters to find a connection between the given input and output pairs;

- b) Unsupervised learning. As the name suggests, there is no teacher or supervisor to monitor the learning process. For these algorithms, only input patterns are available to the network, unlike supervised learning, which has a training set consisting of input and output pairs. From the moment the network establishes harmony with the statistical regularities of the input data, it develops the ability to form internal representations that encode input characteristics and automatically create classes or groups. This type of learning only becomes possible when there is redundancy in the input of data. Without redundancy, it would be impossible to find any patterns or characteristics in the input data.

The structure of an unsupervised learning system can take various forms. It can, for instance, consist of an input layer, an output layer, feedback from the input to the output, and lateral connections between neurons in the output layer. Another example is a multilayer feedforward network, in which free organization proceeds layer by layer. In both examples, the learning process involves repeatedly modifying the synaptic weights of all connections in the system in response to incoming inputs.

To solve a specific task, a network structure and its corresponding training algorithm are employed. Without going into too much detail, the different network structures, activation functions and training algorithms most used are:

- a) Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) is the most popular network today. Its activation function is the logistic function, which can be trained by algorithms such as Conjugate Gradient Descent, Quasi-Newton, Levenberg-Marquardt, Back Propagation, or Delta-bar-Delta.
- b) Radial Basis Function (RBF) is composed of an input layer, a hidden layer of radial units and an output layer of linear units. Typically, the hidden layer of radial units employs an exponential activation function, while the output layer utilizes a linear activation function. RBF networks can be trained using algorithms such as center assignment, deviation assignment, and linear optimization.
- c) A linear network has only two layers: an input layer and an output layer. The activation function can be interpreted as being a weight coming from a unit whose output is always 1 (NASCIMENTO JR and YONEYAMA, 2000, 116). It can be trained using the Pseudo-Inverse technique; that is, the last layer is optimized to obtain a linear function. It can also be trained using principal component analysis.
- d) Kohonen is composed of an input layer and an output layer of radial units. It is mainly used in cluster classification. The activation function is the square root. It can be trained using an unsupervised learning algorithm and (e) others belonging to the Bayesian Networks group, such as the Probabilistic Neural Network (PNN) and Generalized Regression Neural (GRNN).

3 Methodology

3.1 Data

To compare the revenue forecasting performance of the automobile industry, based on multiple linear regression models and neural networks, secondary data collected from ANFAVEA (2002) for the period from 1980 to 2001 were used.

To gain a broader understanding of the information collected and facilitate inputs *into* the forecast models, it was decided to transform them into index numbers. For the indexes to be consistent, three properties were observed (Simonsen; Cysne, 1995):

- a) i) or 1;
- b) the index of period t based on period i is the inverse of the index of period i based on period t (time reversal property), and;
- c) The index of period t based on period i is equal to the product of the index of period t based on period t based on the index of period j based on period i (chain property).

Accordingly explained, an index referring to period t based on the period the

following formula gave me: $I_i^t = \frac{V_t}{V_i} \times 100,$

Where V_i is the initial value (base comparison value) and V_t is the value at time t.

The data collected, along with their respective indexes, are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Data collected and their respective indexes (Base = 1980)

Year	Invoicing		Internal Sales		Export		Investment	
	(10 ⁶) US\$	Index	Units	Index	Units	Index	(10 ⁶) US\$	Index
1980	11,999	100	793,028	100	115,482	100	489	100
1981	9,193	76.61	447,608	56.44	157,228	136.15	645	131.90
1982	10,542	87.86	556,229	70.14	120,305	104.18	530	108.38
1983	9,977	83.15	608,499	76.73	132,804	115.00	373	76.28
1984	9,822	81.86	532,235	67.11	151,962	131.59	293	59.92
1985	12,477	103.98	602,069	75.92	160,626	139.09	478	97.75
1986	11,961	99.68	672,384	84.79	132,241	114.51	526	107.57
1987	12,856	107.14	410,260	51.73	279,530	242.06	580	118.61
1988	14,515	120.97	556,744	70.20	226,360	196.01	572	116.97
1989	13,459	112.17	566,582	71.45	164,885	142.78	602	123.11
1990	10,036	83.64	532,791	67.18	120,377	104.24	790	161.55
1991	10,316	85.97	597,892	75.39	127,153	110.11	880	179.96
1992	12,812	106.78	596,964	75.28	243,126	210.53	908	185.69
1993	14,843	123.70	903,828	113.97	249,607	216.14	886	181.19
1994	17,760	148.01	1,127,673	142.20	274,815	237.97	1,195	244.38
1995	17,863	148.87	1,407,073	177.43	189,721	164.29	1,694	346.42
1996	19,297	160.82	1,405,545	177.24	211,565	183.20	2,359	482.41
1997	21,159	176.34	1,569,727	197.94	305,647	264.67	2,092	427.81
1998	20,292	169.11	1,211,885	152.82	291,788	252.67	2,335	477.51
1999	16,858	140.50	1,011,847	127.59	204,024	176.67	1,791	366.26
2000	18,359	153.00	1,176,774	148.39	283,449	245.45	1,651	337.63
2001	21,667	180.57	1,295,119	163.31	318,637	275.92	1,150	235.17

Source: ANFAVEA (2002)

3.2 Multiple Linear Regression

To construct the forecast model, revenue was considered as the dependent variable. Domestic sales, exports and investments were considered as independent variables. The SPSS® (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) statistical package was used to perform the calculations, and the results obtained are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Construction of the forecast model for revenue

	Non-standard coefficients (B)	Standard Error	Standardized coefficients (Beta)	t	Significance Level
(Constant)	28.603	6.307		4,35	0.000
Internal Sales	0.443	0.083	0.604	5.317	0.000
Export	0.232	0.040	0.411	5.882	0.000
Investments	0.01809	0.028	0.072	0.645	0.527

R = 0.972 F_(3,18) = 102.91

R² = 0.9449 p < 0.00000

R² = 0.9357 Estimated standard error = 8.5235

From Table 2, it can be seen that the estimated model for forecasting revenue for the automobile industry will be given:

$$\text{Invoicing} = 28.603 + 0.443 \times \text{Internal sales} + 0.232 \times \text{Export} + 0.01809 \times \text{Investments}$$

The standard errors are estimated at 6.307; 0.083; 0.040, and 0.028 and the values of the "t" statistic are 4.535; 5.317; 5.882, and 0.645, with 18 degrees of freedom (n – 4) for the constant, domestic sales, exports, and investments, respectively.

The critical value of "t", taken from the "t" distribution table with 18 degrees of freedom and significance level $\alpha = 5\%$, for a two-tailed test is 2.1009. Since the calculated value of "t" is greater than the critical value, except for the "investment" variable, the null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, a significant linear relationship exists between revenue and the variables represented by domestic sales and exports. It is not representative of the "investment" variable, which can be excluded from the "revenue" predictive function.

Another measure to examine the significance of the linear relationship between revenue and the independent variables represented by domestic sales, exports and investment is the test given by the "F" statistics.

As shown in Table 2, the statistic "F_(3,18)" equals 102.906. The critical value of F, with 3 and 18 degrees of freedom (n – 4), taken from the distribution table "F" with a significance level of $\alpha = 5\%$, is equal to 3.16, which is much lower than the calculated value of 102.906. Therefore, the relationship between revenue and independent variables is significant. However, the "t" test revealed that the variable "investment" was not significant at a 5% significance level. Another inference related to the intensity of the relationship is provided by the correlation coefficient, denoted as R². It can be seen that

R2 equals 0.9449, which means that the data have a good fit to the function since the R2 coefficient can vary between 0 and 1. Nevertheless, to avoid erroneous conclusions caused, e.g., by multicollinearity between the variables, the Durbin-Watson test was performed, as shown in Tables 3 and 4.

Table 3: Root Mean Square Error and Durbin -Watson (DW) test

YEAR	Invoicing Real (1)	Predictive Billing (2)	Error (e _i) (1) – (2)	e _{i-1}	(e _i – e _{i-1})	(e _i – e _{i-1}) ²	Squared Error (e _i) ²
1980	100.00	97.9969	2.0031				4.012
1981	76.61	87.6650	-11.0550	2.0031	-13.0581	170.514	122.213
1982	87.86	85.8812	1.9788	-11.055	13.0338	169.880	3.916
1983	83.15	90.7380	-7.5880	1.9788	-9.5668	91.524	57.578
1984	81.86	90.0338	-8.1738	-7.588	-0.5858	0.343	66.811
1985	103.98	96.3677	7.6123	-8.1738	15.7861	249.201	57.947
1986	99.68	94.7635	4.9165	7.6123	-2.6958	7.267	24.172
1987	107.14	109.9589	-2.8189	4.9165	-7.7354	59.836	7.946
1988	120.97	107.4123	13.5577	-2.8189	16.3766	268.193	183.811
1989	112.17	95.7024	16.4676	13.5577	2.9099	8.468	271.182
1990	83.64	85.5444	-1.9044	16.4676	-18.372	337.530	3.627
1991	85.97	90.8822	-4.9122	-1.9044	-3.0078	9.047	24.130
1992	106.78	114.2832	-7.5032	-4.9122	-2.591	6.713	56.298
1993	123.70	132.6600	-8.9600	-7.5032	-1.4568	2.122	80.282
1994	148.01	151.3944	-3.3844	-8.96	5.5756	31.087	11.454
1995	148.87	151.7303	-2.8603	-3.3844	0.5241	0.275	8.181
1996	160.82	158.5019	2.3181	-2.8603	5.1784	26.816	5.374
1997	176.34	185.6327	-9.2927	2.3181	-11.6108	134.811	86.354
1998	169.11	163.7369	5.3731	-9.2927	14.6658	215.086	28.870
1999	140.50	132.8697	7.6303	5.3731	2.2572	5.095	58.221
2000	153.00	157.5644	-4.5644	7.6303	-12.1947	148.711	20.834
2001	180.57	169.4102	11.1598	-4.5644	15.7242	247.250	124.541
TOTAL	2650.73	2650.73	0	59.443	59.443	2189.769	1307.754
MEAN SQUARE ERROR							59.443

As shown in Table 3, the Mean Squared Error is equal to 59.443. On the other hand, applying the Durbin Watson (DW) test, which is given by: $[(e_i - e_{i-1})^2 / (e_i)^2]$, we obtain: $(2,189.769 / 1,307.754) = 1.67445$. The Durbin -Watson (DW) critical values are shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Critical values – Durbin -Watson (DW)

			α= 5%	α= 1%
Sample size	22	d _{lower}	1.05	0.83
Independent variables	3	d _{superior}	1.66	1.40

Thus, it is observed that there is no problem of autocorrelation or multicollinearity at significant levels of 5% and 1%, as the calculated DW statistic (1.67445) is greater than the critical DW value, as shown in Table 4.

3.3 Neural Networks

“Statistica – Neural Networks” from StaSoft Inc. was used. When using this software, it was important to keep in mind that data analysis in a neural network is presented as a “black box”. The focus was not on model parameters such as weights, significance levels or model adjustment indices, but on making the best use of the practical application in solving the problem. When using the neural network package “Statistica – Neural Networks”, the supplier recommends the following steps:

- a) Collect a set of data related to the problem. A neural network's solution will only be as good as the data used to train it. If the data is unrepresentative or biased, the network's solution will suffer, and the model generated will not generalize to the population;
- b) prepare data for analysis. Input data must be prepared; that is, out-of-scale or abnormal data must be removed so that their values fall within an acceptable range;
- c) Analyze the various network topologies, including their types and numbers of layers. Often, the best type and dimension (size) of a network for a problem is unknown. The size of a network is related to the complexity of the problem it is designed to solve. The more complex the problem, the greater the demand for larger networks to obtain an appropriate solution;
- d) identify the network topology that best generalizes the problem under study. The success of a network solution is the good generalization of the population studied. When different types of networks are tried, it is convenient to reserve a data set to test the network to make sure that it has not learned the peculiarities of the training data in order to obtain a good generalization, that is, a good fit and;
- e) Finally, manage the identified network for new data. Once the network solution is accepted and established, it is saved to a file for future reference. When new data is found, prediction can be performed by operating and executing the network for the new data.

Therefore, the collected and analyzed data were developed and compared using different neural network models, including the number of neurons and layers, training algorithms, activation functions, number of epochs, type of normalization, and learning rate. Programmed for a set of 15 tests, the different results obtained are shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Different results obtained by applying different neural networks

	Type	Error	Entries	Hiddens	Performance
01	RBF	25.46267	3	1	0.7751657
02	Linear	13.47182	1	-	0.4101257
03	RBF	9.581519	3	2	0.2916923
04	RBF	8.916316	3	4	0.2714413
05	Linear	7.798546	2	-	0.2374129
06	Linear	7.709793	3	-	0.2347109
07	MLP	7.704029	2	1	0.2345354
08	MLP	7.676821	2	2	0.2335299
09	MLP	7.675677	2	3	0.2336467
10	MLP	7.671636	3	5	0.2335468
11	MLP	7.669094	3	2	0.233468
12	MLP	7.667944	2	6	0.2334308
13	MLP	7.662858	3	2	0.2332696
14	MLP	7.655853	3	6	0.2330483
15 *	MLP	5.635789	3	5	0.1714913

* Best result

It was observed that the network that presented the best result was the Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) with 3 input neurons, 5 hidden layers, and 1 output layer, achieving a performance of 0.1714913. In Figure 3, the best-performing neural network is shown.

Figure 3: MPL network: 3:5:1

Source: the authors.

Once the topology of the best-performing network was identified, it was trained. The most popular training algorithm for MLP networks is back-to-back algorithm propagation (Freitas; Souza, 2002). Hence, using the MLP network and the training algorithm, backpropagation, after several training iterations, the results were obtained, as shown in Tables 6 and 7. Table 6 shows the predictive revenue and the mean square error.

Table 6: Predictive Billing and Mean Squared Error

YEAR	Actual Revenue (1)	Predictive Billing (2)	Error (e _i) (1) – (2)	Error Quadratic (e _i) ²
1980	100.000	96.67582	-3.32418	11.050
1981	76.615	76.58133	-0.03338	0.001
1982	87.857	79.30425	-8.55307	73.155
1983	83.149	84.84822	1.699627	2.889
1984	81.857	82.6855	0.828675	0.687
1985	103.984	100.3553	-3.62839	13.165
1986	99.683	97.70482	-1.97848	3.914
1987	107.142	103.6753	-3.46695	12.020
1988	120.968	111.3614	-9.60701	92.295
1989	112.168	99.63841	-12.5293	156.983
1990	83.640	78.77602	-4.86428	23.661
1991	85.974	92.68072	6.706885	44.982
1992	106.776	112.3834	5.607804	31.447
1993	123.702	128.4406	4.738588	22.454
1994	148.012	145.2427	-2.76968	7.671
1995	148.871	146.1774	-2.69333	7.254
1996	160.822	156.605	-4.21674	17.781
1997	176.340	174.1102	-2.22947	4.971
1998	169.114	162.1232	-6.99087	48.872
1999	140.495	126.4433	-14.0517	197.451
2000	153.004	154.0154	1.011019	1.022
2001	180.573	166.3424	-14.2309	202.519
TOTAL	2650.746	2576.17	-74.575	976.245
MEAN SQUARE ERROR				44.375

The back algorithm is observed propagation, presenting a mean square error of 44.375. This data will be important for comparison with the mean square error of linear regression. The sensitivity analysis is shown in Table 7.

Table 7: Sensitivity analysis of MLP neural network

		Inside Sales	Export	Investment
Verification	Rank	1	2	3
	Error	27.49796	18.58897	11.1992
	Ratio	4.127931	2.790533	1.681198
Training	Rank	1	2	3
	Error	27.49796	18.58897	11.1992
	Ratio	4.127931	2.790533	1.681198

Table 7 shows that the “investment” variable is the least significant in forecasting revenue, i.e., it has the lowest *ratio*. This fact was already demonstrated in multiple linear regression analysis.

4. Analysis Of Results

Table 8 presents the absolute square error and the annual mean square error for the period 1980-2001 when using revenue forecasting based on multiple linear regression and multilayer neural networks. Perceptron (MLP) with 3 input neurons, 5 hidden layers and an output layer. The training algorithm applied to the MLP used was backpropagation.

It is observed that for the period studied, the revenue forecast based on neural networks presented an annual Mean Square Error of 44.375, which corresponds to a 33.9% reduction compared to the annual Mean Square Error when using multiple linear regression. This result demonstrates the advantage of using the neural network technique in problems involving the construction of forecast models, as previously predicted by Braga et al. (2000, p. 227).

However, some caveats must be placed when obtaining this result:

- 1) When constructing the revenue forecast model using multiple linear regression, the same sample was used for both validation and model testing;
- 2) Therefore, to build the prediction model using the MLP network, whose training algorithm was backpropagation, the same criterion was applied; that is, the group of samples used for training, validation, and testing was the same. This procedure was subject to the problem of overfitting, which means that the network specialized in training patterns and lost its generalization capacity (FREITAS and SOUZA, 2002). On the other hand, it was observed that overfitting did not occur, as the absolute quadratic error was not zeroed in any case, even after exhaustive training.
- 3) The default of the software "Statistica – Neural Networks" could have been used to obtain the sample groups. The software randomly groups the training, verification, and test samples in a 2:1:1 proportion. Though, this option was discarded since there was no *overfitting problem*, and the study aimed to compare the performance of the revenue forecasting model based on linear regressions and neural networks.

Table 8: Comparison of Mean Squared Error between Multiple Linear Regression and Neural Networks

YEAR	Invoicing			Squared Error	
	<i>Real</i>	<i>Multiple Linear Regression</i>	<i>Neural Networks</i>	<i>Multiple Linear Regression</i>	<i>Neural Networks</i>
1980	100.00	97.9969	96.67582	4.012	11.050
1981	76.61	87.6650	76.58133	122.213	0.001
1982	87.86	85.8812	79.30425	3.916	73.155
1983	83.15	90.7380	84.84822	57.578	2.889
1984	81.86	90.0338	82.6855	66.811	0.687
1985	103.98	96.3677	100.3553	57.947	13.165
1986	99.68	94.7635	97.70482	24.172	3.914
1987	107.14	109.9589	103.6753	7.946	12.020
1988	120.97	107.4123	111.3614	183.811	92.295
1989	112.17	95.7024	99.63841	271.182	156.983
1990	83.64	85.5444	78.77602	3.627	23.661
1991	85.97	90.8822	92.68072	24.130	44.982
1992	106.78	114.2832	112.3834	56.298	31.447
1993	123.70	132.6600	128.4406	80.282	22.454
1994	148.01	151.3944	145.2427	11.454	7.671
1995	148.87	151.7303	146.1774	8.181	7.254
1996	160.82	158.5019	156.605	5.374	17.781
1997	176.34	185.6327	174.1102	86.354	4.971
1998	169.11	163.7369	162.1232	28.870	48.872
1999	140.50	132.8697	126.4433	58.221	197.451
2000	153.00	157.5644	154.0154	20.834	1.022
2001	180.57	169.4102	166.3424	124.541	202.519
TOTAL	2650.73	2650.73	2576.17	1307.754	976.245
			Mean Square Error	59,443	44.375

5 Conclusions

The results obtained in this study showed that the model based on neural networks outperformed the forecasting model based on multiple linear regression in forecasting revenue for the automotive industry. The superiority of the model based on neural networks was confirmed by the lower Mean Squared Error. Another interesting result that was observed was the non-significance of the variable “investment” when using both multiple linear regression and neural networks.

Given the similarity of the results obtained, the alternative of modeling with Artificial Neural Networks becomes attractive, as these are characterized by non-parametric modeling, which requires little understanding of the process itself. Modeling can be done using only samples of input and output values of the system at regular intervals, as stated by Braga et al. (1998, 227).

Finally, the results obtained allow us to suggest that:

- a) The neural network model represents a good alternative forecasting instrument, which can help managers in decision-making and organizational strategic planning;

- b) (b) be used in future studies, consequently incorporating it into the body of knowledge at the service of science and technology.

Bibliographical References

ANFAVEA 2002. **Statistical Yearbook of the Brazilian Automobile Industry**. São Paulo: Associação Nacional de Fabricantes de Veículos Automotivos, 2002.

BRAGA, Antonio de Pádua, LUDEMIR, Teresa Bernarda, CARVALHO, André Carlos Ponde de Leon Ferreira. **Neural and Artificial Networks: Theory and Applications**. Rio de Janeiro: LTC Editora, 2000.

CARTACHO, Marcelo Soares; SOUZA, Antônio Artur. **The use of a model composed of genetic algorithms and neural networks in the portfolio selection process**. Salvador: XXVI ENANPAD 2002, September 22 to 25, 2002.

FREITAS, Sander Oliveira; SOUZA, Antônio Artur. **Use of a Model Based on Neural Networks for Option Pricing**. Salvador: XXVI ENANPAD 2002, September 22 to 25, 2002.

GUJARATI, Damodar N. **Basic Econometrics**. São Paulo: Makron books. 2000.

HAYKIN, Simon. **Neural Networks, Principles and Practice**. Porto Alegre: Editora Bookman, 2nd^{edition}, 2001.

HILL, Carter, GRIFFITHS, William, JUDGE, George. **Econometrics**. São Paulo: Ed. Saraiva, 2000.

LEVINE, David M., BERENSON, Mark L., STEPHAN, David. **Statistics: Theory and Applications**. Rio de Janeiro, LTC, 2000.

LOESCH, Cláudio; SARI, Solange T. **Neural Networks: Fundamentals and Models**. Blumenau: FURB Publishing, 1996.

MOLITERNO, D. **Carmakers promise to invest R\$95 billion in Brazil, encouraged by Chinese competition and government program**. 2024, Available at: <<https://www.cnnbrasil.com.br/economia/macroeconomia/montadoras-prometem-investir-r-95-bi-no-brasil-instigados-por-competicao-chinesa-e-programa-do-governo/>>. Accessed on: 20/01/2025.

NASCIMENTO JR, Cairo L; YONEYAMA, Takashi. Artificial Intelligence, in Control and Automation. São Paulo: Editora Edgard Blucher Ltda / FAPESP, 2000.

OHMAE, Kenichi. **Returning to Strategy**. Rio de Janeiro: Editora Campus, 2nd^{edition}, 1998.

PORTUGAL, Marcelo S. & FERNANDEZ, Luiz GL. **Artificial Neural Networks and Forecasting of Economic Series: An Introduction**. Mimeograph.

SILVA, Cleide. **Brazilian factories are among the most modern** in the world. São Paulo: OESP – Economics notebook, automobile industry, July 23, 2000, page B7.

SIMONSEN, Mario H. & CYSNE, Rubens C. **Macroeconomics**. Rio de Janeiro: Ed. FGV/Atlas, 1995.